

**PECULIARITIES OF WORKING WITH VIDEO FILMS IN THE PROCESS OF
TEACHING ENGLISH**

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Abstract

The article examines the peculiarities of using video films in the process of teaching English. Particular attention is paid to the stages of working with video materials, the development of students' communicative competence, and the effectiveness of audiovisual technologies in foreign language teaching.

Keywords: teaching, English language, video materials, audiovisual technologies, communicative competence.

Annotatsiya

Maqolada ingliz tilini o'qitish jarayonida videofilmlardan foydalanishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Video materiallar bilan ishlash bosqichlari, talabalarning kommunikativ kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish hamda xorijiy tilni o'qitishda audiovizual texnologiyalarning samaradorligiga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: o'qitish, ingliz tili, video materiallar, audiovizual texnologiyalar, kommunikativ kompetensiya.

Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются особенности использования видеофильмов в процессе обучения английскому языку. Особое внимание уделяется этапам работы с видеоматериалами, развитию коммуникативной компетенции студентов и эффективности аудиовизуальных технологий в обучении иностранному языку.

Ключевые слова: обучение, английский язык, видеоматериалы, аудиовизуальные технологии, коммуникативная компетенция.

In the modern world, it is necessary to keep pace with the rapid development of society and technology. Therefore, a modern lesson should be progressive, engaging, informative, and creative. This requires a creative approach, the ability to use technical teaching aids, and knowledge of innovative educational technologies.

One of the main objectives of teaching English is the development of speaking skills. Consequently, the primary goal of using video materials in English language teaching is the development of oral and written speech. Methodologists traditionally divide the process of presenting video materials into several stages. Thus, Yu.A. Komarova considers the functioning of video fragments in the educational process as a system of supports aimed at forming specific communicative skills. She distinguishes their functions according to the stages of classroom work:

1. Video fragment as a content support (VF-1);
2. Video fragment as a semantic support (VF-2);
3. Video fragment as a stimulus (VF-3).

Taking into account the functions of video fragments at each stage, Yu.A. Komarova identifies the development of monologic speaking skills in the following way:

1. The ability to express one's thoughts in monologic form with the support of VF-1;
2. The ability to develop a monologic speaking strategy with the support of VF-2;
3. The ability to produce independent monologic speech with the support of VF-3.

At each stage, Yu.A. Komarova proposes a complex of gradually complicated exercises based on various modes of presentation: audio track only, video track only, and simultaneous use

of audio and video tracks. For activities involving only the audio track, the following tasks are suggested:

- listen and imagine what is happening on the screen;
- listen and describe the character, compare your imagination with the actual video.

When silent video fragments are presented, the following tasks may be applied:

- watch and describe the events to those who have not seen the video;
- watch and provide voice-over narration;
- watch and role-play the situation.

J. Véhage distinguishes several cycles of exercises connected with the demonstration of films both with and without sound.

Preparatory Stage

At this stage, students complete listening exercises based on dialogues that will later appear in the film without visual support. In addition, students prepare lists of questions related to the film content.

Interactive Group Exercises Before Viewing

- brainstorming activities;
- development of a complete scenario;
- discussion of the film title.

Viewing the Film Without Sound

- description of individual frames using freeze-frame activities;
- prediction of the content of the next scene.

Viewing the Film With Sound

- identifying words from a suggested list that students can both “see” and “hear”;
- preparing questions for communication and discussion;
- reconstructing the text and content of the video fragment through group work.

Post-Viewing Activities

- arranging exercises according to the logical sequence of events in the film;
- answering oral or written questions;
- completing gap-fill exercises;
- creating students’ own video films.

Based on the traditional classification of stages in working with video materials, as well as the approaches proposed by Yu.A. Komarova and J. Véhage, four main stages may be identified:

1. Preparatory or pre-viewing stage;
2. Demonstration or while-viewing stage;
3. Post-viewing stage aimed at checking comprehension;
4. Creative stage focused on the development of language and speaking skills.

Each stage includes a number of tasks whose successful completion determines the effectiveness of the audiovisual learning process.

I. Pre-Viewing Stage

Objectives of the Stage

- to motivate students and involve them actively in the learning process;
- to eliminate possible difficulties in understanding the text and prepare students for successful completion of tasks.

At this stage, linguistic and semantic difficulties are removed. Teachers may introduce proper names that could cause difficulties during viewing and explain the events or circumstances presented in the video material.

The teacher may briefly present the main plot of the video fragment, focusing students’ attention on issues that will later be discussed during the post-viewing stage. Video materials can

also be used as a concluding activity for a series of lessons devoted to a particular topic. Students may receive preliminary assignments related to the topic, which logically prepare them for watching the video. Preliminary reading of texts and discussion of issues related to the same topic in both the native and foreign language also contribute to increasing students' motivation, especially when the video material introduces novelty and new perspectives.

II. While-Viewing Stage

Objective of the Stage

The aim of this stage is to ensure the further development of students' linguistic, communicative, and sociocultural competences according to their real abilities in foreign-language communication.

The demonstration of the film should be accompanied by active learning activities. At this stage, exercises are aimed at searching for, identifying, recording, and transforming specific language material such as vocabulary, grammar, and phonetics. In this case, not only the formulation of the task but also the content of the exercise determines its effectiveness. Students may also take notes while watching the film, which can later be used during post-viewing activities.

III. Post-Viewing Stage

Objective of the Stage

The purpose of this stage is to use the original video material as a basis for the development of productive speaking and writing skills.

At this stage, the effectiveness of the guidelines provided during the pre-viewing stage is assessed, together with the language and speech means presented in the video material. The proper sequence of presenting video materials and the correct formulation of tasks contribute significantly to the effectiveness of using video in English language teaching.

The use of video is a unique means of teaching English at all stages of language learning in secondary school. The effectiveness of video materials in English lessons was confirmed during teaching practice conducted at Mogilev Gymnasium No. 3 in class 6 "G". During the practice, video materials on the topic "Historical Facts and Inventions" were widely applied. The selected materials included videos about the wonders of the Ancient and New Worlds, inventions of humankind, and virtual excursions to Ancient Rome and Egypt.

While studying historical facts, the video materials served as visual aids and supplements to the main textbook *Magic Tour* for sixth-grade students edited by N.V. Yukhnel, E.V. Bushueva, and others. Video materials were used both for introducing new vocabulary items and for reinforcing topic-related vocabulary and grammatical structures such as the Past Simple Passive.

During the study of the topic *The Time Machine*, the virtual excursion *Ancient Egypt* helped create an atmosphere of immersion into the period of Tutankhamun and the world of the pharaohs. The video fragment, logically connected with the lesson topic, became a kind of "time machine," enabling students to experience the historical atmosphere more vividly.

Before watching the video, students were given the following instruction: "Watch the film and say whether you would like to visit Egypt." After viewing, students completed an exercise containing true and false statements from the textbook *Magic Tour*. The video excursion *Ancient Egypt* is a short seven-minute fragment containing information about the construction of the pyramids, the Sphinx, Tutankhamun, and the life of ancient Egyptians. The fragment is presented in English using simple vocabulary familiar to students.

The video excursion *Ancient Rome* was used while introducing the history of Ancient Rome. The excursion contains information about the legend of the foundation of Rome and an overview of the city's main attractions. At the pre-viewing stage, students were asked to recall facts about Ancient Rome, while during viewing they had to answer the question: "Who founded Rome and

when?” At the post-viewing stage, students completed the following task: match the sentences with the pictures and arrange them in the correct order using information from the video excursion Ancient Rome. The excursion lasts approximately eight minutes and contains the legend of Romulus and Remus, as well as information about the city’s major landmarks. The video is presented in English and includes grammatical structures in the Past Simple Passive tense.

The final lesson on the topic Historical Facts and Inventions was organized in the form of a video quiz using the video materials 7 Wonders of the Ancient World and 7 Wonders of the New World.

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